

ANALYSIS OF ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS AND THEIR APPLICATION IN FASHION DESIGN

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Abstract. *The article provides an analysis of architectural elements, the laws of their use in clothing design, as well as examples of creativity of designers who combine architectural elements in clothing design.*

Key words: *visual effect, formofashion, minimalism, deconstructivism, postmodernism.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of the fashion industry, changing trends and the possibility of selling products allow many architects to operate in the field of fashion. The development of technologies, the search for new means of expression, materials, visual effects - all this is breaking the boundaries between fashion and architecture.

Fashion and architecture come from the same point. Clothing and buildings serve as a means of protection, expression and preservation of the human body. Architects and designers create a shell for a person with only one difference: the first is static, the second cannot be without dynamics. A project for designers is the human body.

In recent years, the relationship between fashion and architecture has become more interesting. The development of technology for the production of materials and computer programs has reduced the boundaries of each field. In many cases, the intellectual principles specific to architecture are also used in fashion [1].

METHOD

Style is closely related to fashion, but it is distinguished by its presence, distribution width, regulates and directs fashion.

Hallmarks of fashion inspired by architecture include exaggerated proportions and swooping angles and particular attention to construction and shapes. To create a three-dimensional, architectural look, fabrics are often manipulated through pleating, folding, and layering in order to build up the final effect.

Fashion and architecture as artistic visual fields represent ideas of personal, social, and cultural identity, depicting our interests and assuming the role of memento for specific periods. Throughout history the bond between fashion and architecture has been complicated, sometimes unpredictable, but at the same time invigorating and stimulating. The architectural backdrop in fashion is omnipresent, from Fondazione Prada and Louis Vuitton's Foundation to the extravagant cruise fashion shows in out of this world surroundings where the location overpowers the show, and finally in the architecture background of the fashion giants like Pierre Balmain, Gianfranco Ferré and the latest example Virgil Abloh[2].

For several years, Greek artist and architect Victoria Litra has been finding interesting projects for avant-garde architects and bringing them to art. It combines clothing models from the collections of famous fashion houses and architectural examples. As a result, in Victorian works, buildings and clothes acquired a single conceptual whole as an organic complement and continuation of each other.

That's why the name of the project is formofashion ("harmony of form and fashion") (Fig. 1)[3].

Formofashion. Figure 1

In the presentation of Victorian works, he emphasized that architecture and clothing have one functional meaning - to protect the human body. Therefore, they have a lot in common.

As Coco Chanel said - "the only difference in fashion and architecture is in proportions." Based on this, Victoria develops new approaches to the aesthetics of clothing and building design (Fig. 2).

Figure 2

His works show different styles. For example, in the elements of clothing and buildings - folds, shapes, lines, prints, and easily predictable minimalism, deconstructivism, postmodernism (Fig. 3).

Figure 3

Fashion is always inspired by new forms and unexpected changes in architecture. And in fashion design, many things are created according to the laws of architecture. Looking at the work of Victoria Litra, you will understand how obvious this is. Buildings suddenly start moving as models. And vice versa: on the catwalk, the models freeze and turn into architectural objects. Together, it all looks fantastic (Figure 4)!

Victoria Litra's model. Figure 4

Architecture and fashion grow from the same root, even if at first glance there is little in common between clothes and the house. When I see my ideas come to life in just a few weeks, I feel deep satisfaction, - says the modeler - Oscar de la Renta architect Fernando Garcia.

This led me to switch from architecture to fashion design. But I still use my knowledge of architecture, which seems particularly accurate when it comes to proportions. There should be balance in the facade of the building and in the clothing (Fig. 5) [5].

Oscar de la Renta, Autumn-Winter 17/18. Figure 5

Both fashion and architecture work with a combination of textures and materials, taking into account the laws of gravity and optics. This is especially noticeable when professional architects enter the adjacent field of the fashion industry. In 2006, the legendary Zaha Hadid created her own bag for Louis Vuitton - its smooth curved surface is reminiscent of the Heydar Aliyev Center in Baku, and the embossed LV symbols are somewhat similar to the light mosaic depicted on the wall of the Beethoven concert hall in Germany (Fig. 6) [5].

Zaha Hadid for Louis Vuitton. Figure 6

RESULTS

This style later became popular and widespread among many designers. Over time, the presentation of architecture and clothing design in their collections began to be seen more often on the podiums. Even definitions and classifications of this style have started to be given by designers.

Certain artistic styles are formed in each period of human development. In all historical artistic styles, the stylistic unity of costume and architecture, its elements and room decors, the influence of the urban area, and therefore the technique of architects, which is an important element of the style, are similar. There are stylistic connections between the costume and architecture, expressed by the similarity of the silhouettes, the unity of the main scheme of the interior elements. Designer Tom Ford says that "clothes and buildings are the shell in which a person lives." In addition, they naturally use such means of expression: regardless of the period of style, every fashion is a reflection of architecture and vice versa. Thus, many fashion images of the 1960s are represented by buildings that do not match them, and it is not difficult to imagine a playful figure flight of the architecture of that time in the costumes of the Rococo period[3].

The table below shows examples of collections of several world-renowned designers combining architecture and fashion.

1 Table

№	A brief introduction to the creation sample	An example of creativity
1	Gareth Pugh Spring 2009 Sir Norman Foster, Hirst Building, New York.	
2	Dolce & Gabbana Spring-Summer 2012 Notre Dame de Reims Cathedral, France.	

3	<p>Laura Biagiotti Spring 2012 Leaning Tower of Pisa in Tuscany, Italy.</p>	
4	<p>Chinti & Parker Meets Patternity 2013.</p>	
5	<p>Guy Laroche 2014 Frank Gehry. Beekman Tower, New York.</p>	
6	<p>Guillaume Henri 2014 1911 Guimaras windows Paris.</p>	
7	<p>Jean Paul Gaultier Spring-Summer 2009.</p>	

8	<p>Givenchy Autumn-Winter 2008 Gothic period building.</p>	
9	<p>Balenciaga Spring 2008 Guggenheim Museum, Bilbao, Spain.</p>	
10	<p>Acris Spring 2008 Peter Eisenman, Holocaust Memorial, Berlin.</p>	
11	<p>Chloe Spring-Summer 2016.</p>	
12	<p>Dior Haute Couture Autumn 2014 Interior of Esterházy Palace, Hungary.</p>	

13	Givenchy Autumn-Winter 2008 Peterborough Cathedral.	
14	Gucci Spring 2008 Antoni Gaudi, Park Guell, Barcelona, Spain.	
15	Lara Miller 2010 Gene Banda, Aqua Tower, Chicago.	
16	Paco Rabanne Autumn 2013 Guggenheim Museum, Bilbao, Spain.	
17	Zaha Hadid, Milly Spring-Summer 2016 Heydara Alieva Center, Baku.	

18	Marchesa Autumn-Winter 2008.	
19	Alexander McQueen Spring 2008 Sydney Opera House.	
20	KTZ Spring 2013 Sammezzano Lessio Castle in Regello, Italy.	
21	Yasutoshi Ezumi Spring-Summer 2016.	
22	Philip Lim Spring-Summer 2016.	

23	Zaha Hadid 2012 Zaha Hadid Headquarters Thyssen Krupp, Berlin.	
24	Marchesa Autumn-Winter 2008 Kawasaki Daisy.	

DISCUSSION

Figure 7

It is clear from the above picture that many parts of architecture can be used in fashion design. For example, the ornaments used in architecture, graphics,

examples of painting, the shape of architecture, the appearance and colors of the materials used are among them. Looking to architectural elements as a source of inspiration can be difficult for many designers because it is very difficult to express architecture as much as possible in clothing. However, such examples of creations stand out on catwalks in a unique and unrepeatable way.

It is possible to consider several ways of using examples of painting, ganch carving and wood carving used in architecture in clothes. For example, it is possible to print a pattern on the fabric used in clothing, or to describe it by cutting it in certain parts of the clothing details with the help of a laser device. In addition to the above, it is possible to depict architectural ornaments on clothes using the embroidery method.

To express the shape of the architecture, the material can be heat treated or additional seams can be used.

CONCLUSION

Based on the information given above, it can be concluded that architecture and fashion are two different forms of art and have many common theories and methods. If they are connected together, very beautiful designs are created. Combining "Architecture" and "Fashion" can be a complex process for designers, and the resulting creations are unique.

REFERENCES

1. Zolotukhina A.M. *Взаимосвязь современной моды и архитектуры. На примере архитектуры Японии*. MBU DO "Center for Aesthetic Education", Belokurikha, Russia.
2. Kristina G. (2019) *Architectural Fashion or Fashionable Architecture*. MintSquare.
3. Perevalov I.E. *Связь архитектуры и костюма стиля классицизм* (master dissertation).

Journals

4. “Мода и стиль” article Harper's Bazaar.
5. Design-Mate online magazine.

Website

6. Academia.edu